

HSbooster.eu
Horizon Standardisation Booster

EUOS Standards Academy: Towards the future of education on standardisation

13 June 2023 | 15:00 - 16:00 CEST

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The HSbooster.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) - under grant agreement no 101058391.

HSbooster.eu Training Academy – objectives

Objectives

- The task of the HSbooster.eu Training Academy is to make standardisation closer to researchers through a wide range of training activities and tools (tailored-made texts, case studies, user stories, success stories, serious games, webinars, workshops, and training sessions).
- The HSbooster.eu Training Academy aims to support the HSbooster.eu services and to develop a network of standardisation experts, professionals and researchers.
- All materials created during HSBooster.eu will be freely available as possible to secure IP.

HSbooster.eu Training Academy will provide an efficient mechanism for training – knowledge, expertise and skills.

HSbooster.eu Training Academy

target audience what we learned, evolved and adapt

Specific but not homogenous target audience: Researchers

Target group general characteristics

- impartial
- analytic view
- critical thinking (so what?)
- transmission of their research results (message) through research papers (IF, H index, I index)
- focus on research
- they learn from research

How to train researchers?

The content analysis of interviews with 21 researchers (random sample) suggests:

- They need a **broader understanding** of standardisation (influence on affective factors – attitudes, motivation or values)
- **Motivation** might be a problem. How can that help me? What for?
- Used to **the academic style** of communication.
- **Lack of time** for advancing in something other than their core research area
- Interested in **expanding their networks** (for future project submissions)

Based on an analysis of 32 projects' potential training needs:

- Some projects have a *particular standardisation strategy*
- some projects have a *vague picture of what they want*
- Variety of sectors*

Analysis of 54 experts' needs for training support:

- Some experts have *remarkable experience, and some are less experienced*
- Variety of sectors*

Challenge: Researchers in PC - wide variety of group dynamics & different types of PC – how to make closer standardisation to all of them

Methodology: Placing “why” before “how”

the HSBooster.eu Training Academy is connecting three worlds:

Focus: Experience

To establish a path for learning from the experiences of standardisation experts & HORIZON Projects with experience in standardisation through case studies, success stories, and use cases.

Focus: Practice

Establish and maintain links with standardisation training providers and training material developed by ESOs (CEN, CENELEC, ETSI), EU-based NSBs and all other organisations willing to make standardisation closer to researchers.
(SDOs, standardisation professionals)

Focus: Basics

Theory (Academia). To systematise relevant theory and academic research papers on standardisation to become training material for researchers.

How to build expertise in standardisation

Expertise: "a dynamic state, domain-specific, and the key components of expertise are **knowledge, experience, and problem-solving** (Swanson, 2007)

HSbooster.eu training academy progress Y1

Jumpstart your experience with our training packs!

For beginner users

New to standards?

Check out our **beginner-level resources!**

Gain a **foundational understanding of standardisation** with easy-to-follow resources.

Perfect for both seasoned professionals and beginners starting out in their careers. Start learning today!

Start learning today!

For intermediate users

Ready to level up your **standardisation knowledge?**

Our **intermediate-level resources** provide **practical insights and strategies** to deepen your understanding and take your skills to new heights.

Whether you're a pro or a newcomer, start exploring our resources today and unlock your potential in standardisation!

Explore now!

For advanced users

Ready to learn from **real-world experiences in standardisation?** Our **advanced-level resources** feature in-depth case studies and practical examples from industry experts.

Gain **valuable insights and apply lessons to your own work**. Explore now and take your skills to the next level!

Level up your skills now!

A critical factor for success is that we have joint effort of **academic researchers, standardisation professionals and experts from the industry.**

Basic knowledge of standardisation

For beginner users

New to standards?

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Gain a **foundational understanding of standardisation** with easy-to-follow resources.

Perfect for both seasoned professionals and beginners starting out in their careers. Start learning today!

Start learning today!

Level: Beginner 1

1. B1 01 WHY DO RESEARCHERS NEED STANDARDS
2. B1 02 WHAT IS STANDARDISATION, AND WHAT ARE STANDARDS?
3. B1 03 WHO DEVELOPS STANDARDS?
4. B1 04 EUROPEAN STANDARDISATION SYSTEM
5. B1 05 LEGAL ASPECTS OF STANDARDISATION - RELATIONSHIP OF STANDARDS AND LAW IN THE EU
6. B1 06 USERS OF STANDARDS
7. B1 07 EFFECTS OF STANDARDS IMPLEMENTATION
8. B1 08 CLASSIFICATIONS OF STANDARDS

Level: Beginner 2

9. B2 01 CONSORTIA-BASED STANDARDISATION
10. B2 02 COMPANY STANDARDISATION
11. B2 03 INTRODUCTION TO STANDARD ESSENTIAL PATENTS (SEP)
12. B2 04 QUALITY INFRASTRUCTURE
- 13. B2 04.1 THE ROLE OF METROLOGY IN QUALITY INFRASTRUCTURE
- 14. B2 04.2 THE ROLE OF STANDARDISATION IN QUALITY INFRASTRUCTURE
- 15. B2 04.3 THE ROLE OF ACCREDITATION IN QUALITY INFRASTRUCTURE
- 16. B2 04.4 THE ROLE OF CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT IN QUALITY INFRASTRUCTURE
- 17. B2 04.5 THE ROLE OF MARKET SURVEILLANCE IN QUALITY INFRASTRUCTURE

STANDARDISATION PRACTICE

For intermediate users

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Explore now!

Intermediate 1

- 18. I1 01 HOW TO FIND THE RIGHT STANDARD
- 19. I1 02 HOW TO PARTICIPATE IN TCS OR WGS
- 20. I1 03 HOW STANDARDS ARE DEVELOPED WITHIN SDOS IN EUROPE
- 21. I1 04 HOW STANDARDS ARE DEVELOPED WITHIN SDOS INTERNATIONALLY
- 22. HOW TO DEVELOP A CERTIFICATION SCHEME?**

Future Action Orientaton material of SDOs?

NSAI for HSbooster.eu

DS

Intermediate 2

Serious game: Serious smiling game

Ivana (me ☺) wrote the game, and House of Knowledge (Magnus and Howard) provides the game's support and digitalisation (as a cardboard game and digital version). **Serious smiling game**. This game aims to develop soft skills needed in standardisation processes, focusing on **argumentation skills, strategic positioning, building compromise_and_common_understanding**.

The Serious Smiley Game

- Role playing & simulation game
- On site and online
- aims to develop soft skills needed in standardisation processes:
argumentation skills, strategic positioning, building compromise and common understanding.
- Collaboration HSbooster.eu & HOK

STANDARDISATION EXPERIENCE

For advanced users

Ready to learn from **real-world experiences in standardisation**? Our **advanced-level resources** feature in-depth case studies and practical examples from industry experts. Gain **valuable insights and apply lessons to your own work**. Explore now and take your skills to the next level!

Level up your skills now!

Would you like to learn more about standardisation in action? Here you can find case studies, use cases and success stories of project participants and standardisation experts on various topics.

Advanced 1: Success stories from research project with experience in standardisation

22. Title of Topic: Unlocking new value from urban biowaste – VALUEWASTE & CWA 17866:2022

Advanced 2 >

24. Title of Topic: Impact of standards on market creation: Case of medical/healthcare robot HAL by Cyberdyne

Future actions: Success stories for Advance 1

- Objective: to collect data related to the project's experience and lessons learned during the development of CWA
- We contacted the partners from mainly academic or research organisations, from the **34 EU-funded** projects: MODENA, SATORI, SMR, DRIVER+, EPOS, SMARTER TOGETHER, COROMA, BRESAER, BIONIC AIRCRAFT, VOLATILE, MONSOON, UNICORN, REACH2020, WISEGRID, ETIP OCEAN 2, SEA-TITAN, EUROBENCH, INBOTS, ARCH, SHELTER, RESILOC, FORMPLANET, ECOBULK, OYSTER, FORESEE, COVR, MIRACLE, SMOOTH, FORMOBILE, VALUEWASTE, AIRPOXY, OASIS, INNOMEM, and TRAIN4SUSTAIN.
- Due to project website issues, we collected data about projects from Cordis, such as projects overview, project areas, partners involved in CWA development, and the list of CWAs per project.
- We received **three responses**. One was negative, and two were positive from projects **VALUEWASTE** and **SPIDIA & SPIDIA4P**.

Lesson learned:

- Now we have initial and structured material. However, we need more case studies, success stories, and use cases.
- The whole process of gaining information is very time-consuming.
- Ex-HORIZON projects are reluctant to share their experience in standardisation.

Future action:

We will contact SDOs involved in CWA and standard development

Constant action: Improving the training academy

Contribute in improving our Training Academy

- 🔗 Would you like to contribute to this training topic?
- 🔗 Would you like suggest other training topics for the Academy?
- 🔗 Would you like to author or co-author new material?
- 🔗 Do you have a standards use case you would like to share?

Please contact us at info@hsbooster.eu

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Save your comment

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Horizon Standardisation Booster

Boosting Plastic Packaging Recyclability: Setting the Right Standards

WEBINAR
27 April 2023 10:00 - 12:00 CEST [Register now!](#)

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Horizon Standardisation Booster

Advancing AI regulation through Standardisation

19th December 14:30 - 16:00 CET **WEBINAR**

Speakers

Nicholas Ferguson Co-Magpi Senior Project Manager & HSbooster.eu Coordinator	Salvatore Scalzo Policy & Legal Officer Artificial Intelligence Policy Development and Coordination at European Commission - DG DNECT	Sebastian Hallensleben Chair of Cen-Cenelec JTC 21 WG2 & Head of Digitalisation and AI at VDE	Emilia Tantor Convener CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG2 & Chief Data and Artificial Intelligence Office at Black Swan Lux
Serena Albertario Project Manager at Helix & KIT/ESME Representative	Klaus Hoekner Managing Director HSBI/Access Austria	Ana Cardoso Project Manager at EWF & Stand4EU Project Coordinator	

Funded by the European Union

standICT.eu 2023
28th April 2023 15:00-16:30 (CEST)
Walk & Talk Webinar
Digital Product Passport Making informed choices and protecting brands

Speakers:

- Silvana Muscella** - From IT to new ICT & StandICT.eu 2023 Coordinator
- Iljas Iakovidis** - Adjunct Digital Aspects of Green Transition at European Commission DG CONNECT
- Jens Gayke** - Chair TWG GPP & Managing Director Standards Council Industrie 4.0
- Benjamin Helfritz** - Head of Quality in Transformation at DIN Deutsche Institut für Normung e.V.
- Susanne Gúth-Orłowski** - Chief Innovation & Solution Officer at Splintix
- Francesca Poggiali** - Chief Public Policy Officer Europe at G3
- Thomas L. Rødding** - Entrepreneur, Diplomas & Strategist at Narveto

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StandICT.eu 2023
ICT STANDARDISATION OBSERVATORY AND SUPPORT FACILITY IN EUROPE

13th October 11:30 (CEST)
Walk & Talk
EU Standardisation Priorities - Quantum Technologies

Speakers:

- Oscar Diez** - Head of Sector Quantum Computing at European Commission
- Richard Pitwon** - Chair IEC TC 86/SC B68 & StandICT.eu 2023 Fellow
- Nicolas Spethmann** - Co-chairs of Cen-Cenelec FGQT
- Nooshin Amirifar** - Project Manager and Secretariat, member of Cen-Cenelec FGQT
- Ray Walshe** - StandICT.eu 2023 EUOS Director
- Jonathan J. Attia** - President at Feynman Foundation and Chair of IEEE P2995 WG

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CEN CENELEC IEC IEEE

We invite experts and all interested to contribute to the HSbooster.eu Training Academy

Contribute to HSbooster.eu Training Academy: Share Your Insights and Make a Difference

Are you passionate about sharing your knowledge and insights to empower others? Join us in improving the [HSbooster.eu Training Academy](#) and contribute your valuable expertise.

We invite you to be part of our mission to enhance the training experience for our community. Your valuable knowledge can help shape and enrich our training materials, making a lasting impact on the learning journey of our participants.

Whether you are interested in authoring new training modules, co-authoring existing materials, or providing feedback and suggestions, your contribution is highly valued. Together, we can create a dynamic and comprehensive training academy that addresses the needs and challenges of our industry.

Join us in empowering individuals, fostering professional growth, and advancing our collective knowledge. Together, let's contribute valuable insights and make a difference in the HSbooster.eu Training Academy.

Choose among our comprehensive training packages tailored to different proficiency levels.

^ Level of expertise: Beginner

Beginner 1 (B1)

- B1-Course 1: [Why do researchers need standards and standardisation?](#)
- B1-Course 2: [What is standardisation, and what are standards?](#)
- B1-Course 3: [Who develops standards?](#)

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows

Training plan M12 – M24

HSbooster.eu Training Series:

- Introduction to standardisation (four training sessions)
 - Standardisation in Practice (three training sessions)
 - Thrive on standardisation (five training sessions)
-

Training plan M12 – M24

	Framework: Online training	Date	Who
Training series: Introduction to standardisation			
1.	Introduction to standardisation 1 Topics: Why do researchers need standards What is standardisation, and what are standards? Who develops standards? Time: 90 + Q&A	Maj, 4 th Bimonthly, on recorded	Ivana Mijatovic, UoB
2.	Introduction to standardisation 2 European Standardisation System Topics: European standardisation system Legal aspects of standardisation - the relationship of standards and law in the EU Time: 90 minutes + Q&A	June, 15th	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ana Kicanovic, University of Belgrade (UoB) •Ashok Ganesh, Director of Market Perspectives & Innovation (CEN – CENELEC) •David Boswarthick, Director of New Technologies at ETSI (ETSI)
3.	Introduction to standardisation 3 User of standards and standards in use Topics: Users of standards Effects of standards Implementation Classification of standards Time: 90 minutes + Q&A	June, 23rd	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ivana Mijatovic, University of Belgrade (UoB) •Maitane Olabarria, Small Business Standards Secretary General (SBS) and •Chiara Giovannini, Deputy general director of the European Association for the Coordination of Consumer Representation in Standardisation (ANEC).

Training plan for discussion M12 – M 24

	Framework: Online training	Date	Who
Training series: Introduction to standardisation			
4.	Introduction to standardisation 4 Topics: Consortia-based standardisation Company standardisation Time: 75 - 105 minutes + Q&A	September	TbD Standardisation professionals in companies
Training series: Standardisation in Practice			
5.	Training Session: Serious Smiley Game (online or onsite) Time: 150 minutes	June, September, October, November, December, TbD	Online assisted by HoK Note: 27 (c) CoP Training in negotiation skills
6.	SDOs for researchers (online) How to find the right standard? How to participate in TCs or WGs? How are standards developed within SDOs in Europe? Time: 45 minutes	October	TbD
7.	Working title: Fast track standardisation (online) CWA, IWA, DIN Spec, NSAI spec	October	TbD

Training plan for discussion M12 – M 24

	Framework: Online training	Date	Who
Training series: Thrive on standardisation			
8.	When is the time for standardisation in the research process?	October	TbD
9.	Certification. How to develop a certification scheme?	September	TbD Inspired by CoP 27 (c)
10.	How to develop a standardisation strategy?	November	TbD Inspired by CoP 27 (c)
11.	Patenting or standardisation? – or both Introduction to standard essential patents (SEP)	December	TbD Inspired by CoP 27 (c)
12.	Building Alliances (of research projects & PP) for standardisation	January – March 2024	TbA
	All modules & game sessions & general standardisation	Design and deliver 20+ targeted training to be delivered to premium service applicants	All modules & game sessions & general standardisation

Thank you

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